

**FEATURES OF EXPRESSING FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS THROUGH
ZOONYM PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE UZBEK, KARAKALPAK
AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.**

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Annotation: The article discusses the semantic characteristics and classification of adjective phraseological units with zoosemic designations. The subjective-evaluative meaning and metaphorical nature of phraseological units with zoosemism are largely related to the anthropocentrism directly expressed in them. The thematic classification of the analyzed phraseological units allows us to identify groups of adjective phraseological units of an anthropocentric direction with a “zoonymic” component.

Key words: zoonyms, phraseological units, family relationships.

The phraseological system of any language includes its national symbols. Differences between two or more languages can only be determined on the basis of their comparative analysis. It goes without saying that the greater the differences between them, the longer will be the genetic characteristics of the compared languages. This process can also go in the other direction, that is, the closer the languages (related languages) are to each other, the more similarities are observed between them.

Every nation has its own culture, and this aspect influence its vocabulary. In this regard, one cannot but agree with the opinion of Yu. E. Bregel: “The aphoristic folklore of a people has its own character, first of all, it is a view, a path of historical development, a worldview, social and poetic aspects of this people”.

However, this does not mean that English does not have topics that exist in other languages. Because expressions embody people's experiences, their life paths and conclusions about life. Therefore, one can observe uniformity or similarity in the patterns of oral folk art. However, as mentioned above, folk expressions are not without their peculiarities. To find out, we studied the components of zoonyms existing in

English, Karakalpak and Uzbek expressions, dividing them into different semantic groups. And in this article we will focus on expressions related to family relationships and identify the semantic features of zoonomic phraseological units.

Family relationships are the basis of human life.

E.g.:

The black crow thinks her own birds white;

Every mother thinks her own gosling a swan;

A crab walks, so walks his children;

If you become a dog, turn into the dog of a wealthy family;

A dog shows affection even to a poor family;

In English expressions, the concept of family is considered divine, and in many cases the image of the dog is invoked as a sign of responsibility and loyalty to it. Warm concern for family is rarely found in English expressions. For most of them, children and families are people in need of economic and financial support. Perhaps this may indicate that they have a very high “I”. But we cannot refuse their family care. F/e :

Charity begins at home; Marriages are made in heaven.

These phrases mean that people should take care of their family first.

If we pay attention to Karakalpak proverbs, more attention is paid to the relationship between husband and wife, parents and children.

At aylanıp qazıǵın tabadı

Eki sıyr sawganniń ayranı bar, eki qatın allganniń wayranı bar

Malı oskenniń murtı õser, ulı õskenniń urtı õser

Atıń olse tayaq bar ,jugin jolda qaldırmastay

Ata õlse ulı bar, mülki wayran bolmastay

Balalı qoyan qashalmas

Ǵarǵa suyerbalasın appaǵım dep, kirpi suyerbalasın jumsaǵım dep

From these examples, we can see that they are very kind to their children and ready to sacrifice themselves for them, and that they lean on their parents in their old

age. Also, we can see that the loyalty of husband and wife to each other is necessary for the family, for them the family is sacred.

The Uzbek people have a special approach to family and mutual respect in the family. Proverbs vividly reflect the relationship between husband and wife, children and their upbringing, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law. Considering that mother-in-law, daughter-in-law, sons-in-law, close relatives and many other family members have lived together since ancient times, let us consider family ties, dividing them into several groups.

1. Husband and wife, their mutual relationship:

Er – xotin – qo’shxo’kiz;

Er – xotin – qo’shqanot;

Er – xotinning urushi – jo’ja – xo’roz urush.

2. The wife and her role in the family

Beva xotinga Buxorodan it hurar;

Ikki sigir olganning ayroni bor, ikki xotinolganning vayroni;

Ikki xotinlikning qulog’I tinmas, eshak minganning – oyog’i;

3. Children and relationships with parents:

You may notice that most of the proverbs are dedicated to children. For example:

Xotininim qiztug’di deb o’pkalanma,sherning erkak urg’ochisi barobar;

Quyvon bolasini botirim der, it bolasini qoplonim;

Qo’zimo’rabo’sar bola yig’lab;

4. Close relatives, relations between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law:

The connection between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law is especially clearly manifested in expressions. For example:

Itningyovi – devona, kelinningyoviqaynona;

Qaynonaga tosh otsang tosholasan, qaynonagaoshbersangosholasan;

Begonabilanquyonovlama,ovlasangham,yoninggaboylama;

It can be seen that the idea of the family of the Uzbek people is multifaceted, which indicates that clan-family relations were formed in ancient times.

Phraseology is the pinnacle of linguistic knowledge, clearly explaining the relationship between language and culture. The image of an animal is found in the phraseology of many languages, and this situation, of course, is not accidental. Because the animal world from the time of human society still lives side by side with people and plays an important role in their lives. It is important that in different countries the image of an animal reflects different qualities. This indicates that each nation has its own individual images. In the above examples, it is clear that all three linguistic examples of proverbs have similar and different aspects, however, it is worth noting that in all three nations, family is the basis of human life.

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